

Chinese Tourists's Behaviors towards Travel and Shopping in Bangkok

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Abstract—The objectives of this study are to study Chinese tourist's Behaviors towards travel and shopping in Bangkok. The research methodology was a quantitative research. The sample of this research was 400 Chinese tourists in Bangkok chosen by the accidental sampling and the purposive sampling. Inferential Statistics Analysis by using the Chi-square statistics. As for the results of this study the researcher found that differences between personal, social and cultural information, i.e., gender, age, place of residence, educational level, occupation, income, family, and main objectives of tourism with behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok towards travel and shopping in Bangkok.

Keywords—Tourists' behavior, Chinese tourists, travelling, expenses in travels.

I. INTRODUCTION

JOURNEY has come along with human beings since the ancient times but it is different in objectives or goals. In the past, human beings took a journey with purposes of making their living, earning their lives and being at wars to seize resources and territories, and after that disseminating religions. Up to now, people travel for relaxing relieving stress from work, so called "travelling for tourism."

Many countries are aware that "tourism" will be the major incomes to their own countries during the regressive economy. For example, Japan permits Thai tourists to travel in the country not longer than 15 days without asking for visa in advance. As a result, it becomes effective because the entry of tourists can stimulate domestic economy very well. Considering Thailand at present, many people probably agree that tourists from China ranked number one visiting Thailand since 2012 with a number of 2,789,345 (accounting for 12.51%). According to the Tourist Statistics, the top 10 international tourist arrivals to Thailand (by nationality) in April 2014 were China, Malaysia, Russia, Laos, the United Kingdom, Australia, Korea, India and Germany, respectively [1] and in July 2014, there were 342,547 Chinese tourists arriving Thailand [2], which is always a largest number visiting Thailand. An increasing number partly came from China changing the economic system from the communist system to the free trade system, resulting in Chinese people to contact foreign countries more [3] and travel outside the country more conveniently. Chinese tourists are ready to spend more money for tourism about 20% per year.

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The reasons that Chinese tourists choose to visit Thailand because of tourist attractions differing from China, for example, historical attractions, cultural attractions, natural attractions, cozy atmosphere, breath of air, sunlight and watercourse, as well as nightlife entertainment that are rarely found in their country. Besides travelling, they can go shopping, buy sacred objects, eat seafood or rare health food, such as, bird's nest and wild animals, all of which are inexpensive when comparing to in China.

Apart from travelling in the beautiful and unique attractions of that country, "shopping" is what attracts tourists to visit regularly. In creating attractive shopping places, we need to understand shoppers' behaviors. According to Paco Underhill, the consumer analyst and the author of *Why We Buy: The Science of Shopping*, [4] the first principle of the science of shopping was the simplest one that is everyone has similar abilities, tendencies, limitations, as well as physical and physiological needs; therefore, retail environment should be established to be appropriate with those qualifications and friendly with uniqueness of human beings. Shoppers are distinct by gender, age, income and preferences. Consequently, any established environments should reflect nature of living things occupying that place. If the appropriate environment can be established and managed, it will be created successfully. If this group of shoppers makes re-purchases, it will result in a continuously increasing number of quality tourists.

The poll of MasterCard Online Shopping on April 4, 2013 surveyed the consumer trend of online shopping in 25 countries during November-December 2012 and found that China was number one in online shopping, followed by New Zealand, Australia, Singapore and South Korea. Changes of purchasing behaviours in China increase confidence in online shopping with only 21.4% feeling uncertain in online shopping, which reduced from 32.8% in 2012 and 35.5% in 2011. Moreover, there was a new perspective among Chinese shoppers by 89.5% considering that online shopping was easy, which increased from 80.8% in 2011[5].

Therefore, the researcher thought that to promote tourism through shopping activities should rely on deeply studying consumer behaviours. This research aimed to study tourism behaviors of tourists in Bangkok Metropolitan and doing activities during tourism so-called "tourism shopping," leading to approaches to promote tourism marketing for Chinese tourists in the future.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Objective of Research

The objective of this research is to study tourism behaviors of Chinese tourists and promote tourism marketing through shopping activities of Chinese tourists towards in Bangkok.

B. Research Methodology

The study on Chinese Tourist's Behaviors towards travel and shopping in Bangkok was a quantitative research by studying and collecting data from document research and survey research. This research mainly aimed to find the solutions to the problem of tourism behaviors of Chinese tourists.

In collecting data, the researcher divided the study into 2 parts: Part 1 was the document research or the secondary research concerning arrival of Chinese tourists, behaviors of Chinese tourists in Thailand, research related with Chinese tourists, behaviors towards travel and shopping in Bangkok; Part 2 was the survey research in collecting data on tourism behaviors towards travel and shopping in Bangkok by distributing the questionnaires to Chinese tourists.

The questionnaire was used as the research instrument, divided into 2 parts: Part 1: Personal, social, and cultural information and Part 2: Questions on behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok. The sample of this research was 400 Chinese tourists in Bangkok by using Taro Yamane's formula [6] with the reliability of 95% and at the significant level of 0.05. The sample group was chosen by the accidental sampling and the purposive sampling.

After verifying the data collected from the questionnaire and completion, the researcher analyzed the data by computerized data processing. The statistical package was used in calculating the statistical values and testing the established hypotheses with the reliability of 95% and at the significant level of 0.05. The statistics used in analyzing the data were as follows:

- i. Descriptive Statistics Analysis was used in describing the data by frequency, showing data in the form of table by percentage to explain personal, social and cultural information, i.e., gender, age, place of residence, educational level, occupation, income, family, and main objectives of tourism. Standard deviation and means were used to described interval scale data.
- ii. Inferential Statistics Analysis was used in found relationship between personal, social and cultural information, i.e., gender, age, place of residence, educational level, occupation, income, family, and main objectives of tourism with behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok towards travel and shopping in Bangkok by using Chi-square. When detecting differences, Scheffe's method was used to perform multiple comparisons for statistical analysis.

III. FINDINGS

In presenting results of data analysis and interpretation, the researcher analyzed and presented data in descriptive tables divided into two parts.

A. Part 1: Descriptive Analysis

- i. Basic information of the respondents, i.e., gender, age, marital status, educational level, current position, and average monthly income.
- ii. Behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok, i.e., number of visiting, objectives of visiting, the person visiting with, travelling preparation, place of residence, frequent duration of visiting, length of visiting, using service at the information center, impressive attractions, souvenirs, average expenses during travelling and re-visiting Bangkok.

TABLE I
 NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE OF BASIC INFORMATION OF THE RESPONDENTS

Basic Information	Number	Percentage
Gender:		
Male	171	42.8
Female	229	57.3
Age:		
Less than 15 years old	13	3.3
15-25 years old	139	34.8
26-36 years old	112	28.0
37-47 years old	65	16.3
48-58 years old	50	12.5
More than 59	21	5.3
Marital Status:		
Single	157	39.3
Married	226	56.5
Divorce	17	4.3
Educational Level:		
Less than Secondary	14	3.5
Secondary	87	21.8
Bachelor's degree	233	58.3
Master's degree	48	12.0
More than Master's degree	18	4.5
Current Position:		
Student	98	24.5
Housewife	44	11.0
Government	42	10.5
Private Officer	93	23.3
Agriculturist	6	1.5
Retire	27	6.8
Freelance	70	17.5
Others	20	5.0
Average Monthly Income:		
Less than 3,000 yuan	104	26.0
3,001- 5,000 yuan	116	29.0
5,001-7,000 yuan	76	19.0
7,001-9,000 yuan	36	9.0
9,001-11,000 yuan	43	10.8
More than 11,000 yuan	25	6.3
Total	100	400

B. Part 2: Inferential Analysis to Test Hypotheses

Hypothesis: Basic information of the respondents, that is, gender, age, marital status, educational level, current position, and average monthly income had relations to behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok.

- i. Basic information of the respondents, i.e., gender, age, marital status, educational level, current position, and

average monthly income was shown by frequency and percentage in Table I.

TABLE II
NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE OF BEHAVIORS OF CHINESE TOURISTS
IN BANGKOK

Tourists' behaviors	Number	Percentage
Number of visiting:		
once	260	65.0
2-4 times	119	29.8
More than 5 times	21	5.3
Objectives of visiting:		
Relaxation	257	64.3
Honeymoon	45	11.3
Education	64	16.0
Relatives	11	2.8
Business	23	5.8
Person visiting with:		
Family	133	33.3
Friends	149	37.3
Lover	69	17.3
alone	49	12.3
Travelling preparation:		
Finding tourism information on their own	221	55.5
Buying Package Tour in China	172	43.0
Buying Package Tour in Thai	7	1.8
Place of residence:		
Beijing	41	10.3
Shanghai	69	17.3
Shenzhen	55	13.8
Guangzhou	69	17.3
Chengdu	35	8.8
Kunming	43	10.8
Xiamen	16	4.0
Guangxi	42	10.5
Others	30	7.5
Frequent duration of visiting:		
December - February	109	27.3
March - May	84	21.0
June - August	97	24.3
September - November	110	27.5
Length of visiting:		
1-3 days	99	24.8
4-6 days	184	46.0
7-9 days	83	20.8
More than 9 days	34	8.5
Using service at the information center:		
Every time	51	12.8
Sometime	152	38.0
Never	197	49.3
Impressive attractions:		
Wat Phra Kaew	106	26.5
Wat Pho	63	15.8
Khao San Road	44	11.0
China Town	20	5.0
Asiatique	25	6.3
Central World	36	9.0
Siam Square	31	7.8
Amusement Park/Zoo	15	3.8
Night Place	42	10.5
Others	18	4.5
Average expenses during travelling :		
Less than 5,000 baht	40	10.0
5,001 - 20,000 baht	151	37.8
20,001 - 40,000 baht	119	29.8
More than 40,001 baht	90	22.5
Re-visiting Bangkok :		
Certainly	162	40.5
Uncertainly	220	55.0
No come again	18	4.5

ii. Behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok, i.e., number of visiting, objectives of visiting, the person visiting with, travelling preparation, place of residence, frequent duration of visiting, length of visiting, using service at the information center, impressive attractions, souvenirs, average expenses during travelling and re-visiting Bangkok was shown by frequency and percentage in Table II.

IV. RESULTS OF DATA ANALYSIS

According to the hypothesis that basic information of the respondents consisting of gender, age, marital status, educational level, current position and average monthly income had relations with behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok, the followings were results of analysis on the relations of behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok with gender, age, marital status, educational level, current position and average monthly income by using the chi-square statistic:

Gender of Chinese tourists had relation with objectives of visiting and the person visiting with, that is, both males and females had objectives of visiting for relaxation nearly the same with 69% of males and 60.7% of females. In case of the person visiting with, most of females travelled with friends whereas most of males travelled with family or cousins.

Age of Chinese tourists had relation with objectives of visiting. All of people in the age of 15-59 had objectives of visiting for relaxation with most of people in the age of 37-59 (73.5%) while people in the age of 15-25 had objectives of visiting for continuing their study about 29.6%.

In term of the person visiting with, 48.7% of people under the age of 15-25 frequently travelled with friends, 33% of people in the age of 26-36 frequently travelled with their beloved, and 48.5% of people in the age of 37-59 frequently travelled with family or cousins.

In term of the travelling preparation, 63.8% of people under the age of 15-25 frequently sought travel information and travelled by themselves whereas 57.4% of people in the age of 37-59 frequently bought the package tour from China in advance.

In term of the average expenses during travelling, the more age the Chinese tourists were in, the more average expenses during travelling they had, that is, 69.8% of people in the age of 37-59 had the average expenses during travelling more than 20,000 baht, 34.8% of the middle-aged people in 26-36 years old had the average expenses during travelling between 5,000-20,000 baht and 15.1% of the youngest group had the average expenses during travelling less than 5,000 baht.

Marital status of Chinese tourists had relation with behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok. 73.9% of the unmarried or single group mostly visited Thailand for the first time with the objectives of visiting for relaxation (62.4%) and continuing their study (26.1%), and frequently travelling with friends (49.7%). In term of the travelling preparation, 69.4% of the single group sought travel information and travelled by themselves and 40.1% travelled for 4-6 days, which was

similar to the married group (49.8%). Lastly, behaviors on spending during travelling for the single group and the married group on average were nearly the same between 5,000-20,000 baht.

Educational level of Chinese tourists had relation with behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok. 46.5% of people with below secondary education mostly travelled with family or cousins and 66.3% bought the package tour from China's travel agencies in advance with the average expenses during travelling between 5,000-20,000 baht. On the contrary, 65.7% of the Chinese tourist group with more than bachelor's degree education mostly travelled with friends and frequently sought travel information and travelled by themselves. In term of the average expenses during travelling, people with below secondary education up to bachelor's degree education had the average expenses during travelling between 5,000-20,000 baht whereas people with more than master's degree education had the average expenses during travelling over 40,000 baht.

Current position of Chinese tourists had relation with behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok. Most of Chinese tourists were students, visited Thailand for the first time, had the objective of visiting for relaxation, frequently travelled with friends during December-February, had the average length of visiting about 4-6 days and had the average expenses during travelling between 5,000-20,000 baht.

Average monthly income of Chinese tourists had relation with behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok. No matter how much the average monthly income they had, most of them visited Thailand for the first time with the objective of visiting for relaxation. Most of Chinese tourists with income less than 3,000 yuan up to more than 11,000 yuan had the objective of visiting for relaxation. In case of the tourists with the average monthly income between 3,000-9,000 yuan, on average they often spent between 5,000-20,000 baht, while the tourists with the average monthly income more than 9,000 yuan often had the expenses during travelling more than 40,000 baht.

V. DISCUSSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The research on behaviors of Chinese tourists towards travel and shopping in Bangkok could be discussed as follows:

1. The analysis on behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok showed that most of them visited Bangkok for the first time with the objective of relaxation and travelling with friends. They prepared their travelling by searching information by themselves and their places of residence were Shanghai and Guangzhou. Time of duration they frequently travelled was between September and November for 4-6 days. Most of them never use the service at the tourist information center. The impressive attraction was Wat Phra Kaew. Mostly they bought bags, NaRaYa bags and crocodile leather bags as souvenirs. Average expenses were between 5,001 and 20,000 baht. Most of them were unusual whether they would visit Bangkok again. Export-Import Bank of Thailand (2013) [7] stated travelling with the tour group arranging the tour

program was convenient readily provided accommodations and tour guides to facilitate in both languages and solving problems. The tourists who travelled to a foreign country for the first time chose to travel with the tour group. The tour group frequently brought the tourists to visit famous places, important attractions or popular attractions, followed by going shopping. Chinese tourists went shopping as the presents for their family, friends, and co-workers. The most popular luxury goods that well-off Chinese tourists bought were wrist watches and ornaments, followed by leatherwork, clothes, cosmetics and electronics appliances. Currently, more than 80% of Chinese tourists searched information on new destinations, accommodations and travelling from the internet, which was consistent with the research of [8] studying behaviors of Chinese tourists in Chiang Mai, Thailand. According to that research, Chinese tourists came from Shanghai, Guangdong, Beijing and Jiangsu, and more than half travelled with employees in the company and friends without using the service of the travel agency. On average, they travelled for 4 days for relaxation and sightseeing. Consistently, [9] studied on opinions and behaviors of 369 Thai tourists towards tourism in Ko Lan, Pattaya and found that they frequently travelled with at least two friends and more than half were impressed of beautiful scenery and wanted to visit Pattaya beach again.

2. The analysis of relations of behaviors of Chinese tourists in Bangkok with personal information i.e., gender, age, marital status, educational level, current position and average monthly income showed that gender of Chinese tourists had relation with objectives of visiting and the person visiting with; age of Chinese tourists had relation with objectives of visiting, the person visiting with, the travelling preparation, and the average expenses during travelling; marital status of Chinese tourists had relation with number of visiting, the objectives of visiting, the person visiting with, the travelling preparation, length of visiting, and the average expenses during travelling; educational level of Chinese tourists had relation with the person visiting with, the travelling preparation, and the average expenses during travelling; current position of Chinese tourists had relation with number of visiting, the objectives of visiting, the person visiting with, frequent duration of visiting, length of visiting, and the average expenses during travelling; and average monthly income of Chinese tourists had relation with number of visiting, the objectives of visiting, and the average expenses during travelling. It was consistent with the concept on external factors affecting to tourists' decisions consisting of reference group which acted as frame of reference or guidelines for people making decisions to buy any products and services, family which was at least 2 people living together and having blood relations, being married, or adopting children, social class which clearly classified people in the society with members of any social classes

would be in the same social status and members of other social classes would be higher or lower classes, and culture in perspectives of consumer behaviors which was a combination of beliefs, values and traditions resulting from learning to determine consumption behaviors of members in a certain society.

In conclusion, the modern society consisted of a variety of lifestyles affecting to various consumption styles, such as, differences between men and women that “Why We Buy: The Science of Shopping” by Underhill Paco stated that women and men were different in almost all aspects. Women had a great satisfaction in what we called “shopping” like wild collectors getting entertainment from surveying, talking, and trying products, whereas men were like hunters when they wanted some products, they would search for them and if they found what they wanted, they would buy immediately, but if they did not found, they would be fidgety and walk away. Therefore, men were less poetic, did not like to ask and spent less time to look. Moreover, [10] added differences between men and women basically came from nature that men liked number, violence and fighting while women focused on emotion, feeling and fineness. So product presentation and advertisements for men and women should be different.

Susan Cave stated [11] that ability to link products with self-concept of consumers was an important characteristic of the markets, especially for products appropriate for only one gender and related with physical appearance.

Shopping behaviors mostly found in all kinds of genders and ages because all of us were consumers and shopping behaviors had effects to thoughts, feelings, viewpoints, and some decisions. Purchasing power could be measured by family income. Generally, shoppers would be happier, healthier and more optimistic than economical people. It was obvious that women were happy every time they went shopping. In case of Chinese tourists, we found that most products were for women. Women liked products giving benefits both in emotional and social, such as, NaRaYa bags, cosmetics, and jewelry, whereas men liked products related with hobbies or leisure time, such as, automobiles and tonic.

Also, ages had effects to travelling and shopping. Cognitive age was an important factor towards consumption behaviors of those people rather than chronological age. Typically, adults in 50-64 years had highest weekly expenses compared with people in all ages. Aging consumers tended to spend most money with medicines and health products or services, including travelling for relaxation. Chinese tourists in Thailand in 15-25 years showed that most of travelling behaviors should focus on teenage group. Therefore, if we preliminarily studied tourist behaviors, we could focus producing goods and services by using five principles proposed by Paco Underhill, that is,

1. Touch: Tourists should have touching, hearing, smelling or tasting during travelling or shopping.
2. Mirror: During going shopping, mirror will reflect how we look and this makes shoppers walk more slowly, which is considered an important selling tool, especially

for Chinese tourists who frequently buy products like clothes, jewelry and cosmetics.

3. Discovery: We should create attractions to tourists or shoppers, i.e., sweet smell of food and desserts to attract them to search for.
4. Talking: We should create atmosphere to support any kinds of talks and discussions, such as, clothes than can attract husband, wife and friends.
5. Recognition: People will go shopping in the places that they feel they are needed. Any contacts the employees start first, i.e., greeting will increase possibilities for tourists or shoppers to buy something.

Finally, the most important of the study on tourism behaviors and shopping of Chinese tourists was “worthiness” which would be interpreted according to gender, age, status, income, education and lifestyle of each group of tourists. Therefore, if we want to give importance for any group of tourists, we probably deeply study and understand specific behaviors in the future. Suggestion for further study is comparison of tourism types or choosing products with other groups of tourists.

Tourism entrepreneurs need to understand very well about important roles of this industry which has long been history and has reliable service quality [12].

A. Research Suggestions

1. The results showed that most of Chinese tourists visited Bangkok for the first time with the objective of relaxation and travelling with friends. They prepared their travelling by searching information by themselves and their places of residence were Shanghai and Guangzhou. Time of duration they frequently travelled was between September and November for 4-6 days. Most of them never use the service at the tourist information center. The impressive attraction was Wat Phra Kaew. Mostly they bought NaRaYa bags and crocodile leather bags as souvenirs. Average expenses were between 5,001 and 20,000 baht. Most of them were unusual whether they would visit Bangkok again. Therefore, the related units should have plans in providing the training to tourism companies to acquire tourism knowledge that changes from time to time, i.e., preparing information of tourism, tourism duration, souvenir shops and service training for staff.
2. As Thailand is one of China’s outbound tourism destination, most of Chinese tourists behave like pushy, loud, impolite, unruly which might be the norm in China, but it isn’t the norm in most of the rest of the world and tourists need to know that. They are just being themselves – they are being Chinese. It caused “Culture Shock” when experiencing an unfamiliar way of life due to visiting new country. Therefore, the next research paper should have a good guideline or instruction for changing Chinese tourists’ bad behavior especially giving the instruction for Chinese tourists on travel etiquette to tour guides and tourists. Then, they have to respect all religious men such as abbots (Buddhism), monks (Buddhism), priests

(Christian), and Imams (or Islamic priests). Moreover, requesting tourists do not touch all the paintings, warn against using public property as lavatory facilities and walk way and breakpoint. Importantly, tour guides are being given the good behavior manual or instruction to encourage their tourists; this is a way to create positive images of Thailand by telling them how to act in Thailand appropriately to avoid local complaints.

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